

Analyzing Temporal Changes in Land Use in Response to Population Growth in Malegaon Tehsil of Nashik District

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Abstract

Land is considered an essential natural resource, fundamental for economic and social development. Land utilization is the way in which land is used to manage a variety of human uses (agriculture, forestry, pasture, mining, transportation, industrial, commercial, residential, recreational etc) at a point in time and space. Human needs have a profound influence on the patterns of land use ranging from agrarian and settlements to transportation, defence, and recreation. Rapid population growth increases pressure on finite land resources, which calls for periodic reconsideration of land use patterns. Since land is understood as a limited resource, it becomes a critical component of short-term and long-term land use planning. Malegaon city, the administrative headquarters of Malegaon tehsil, sits in Nashik district, Maharashtra, making it a prime site for land use analysis as it straddles the Mumbai–Agra National Highway (NH-3). The tehsil area, with an area of 1,818.44 sq. km and a population of 955,594 with a population density of 526 persons per sq. km (Census 2011). The proposed research seeks to determine the causes and impacts of land use change and emerging geo-environmental issues in the region.

Keywords: Land use, temporal Variation, Recreation.

1. Introduction

Land is one of the most fundamental and finite natural resources, playing an equally critical role in determining human economic, social and cultural development. Land use refers to the surface utilization of both developed and vacant land within a specific area at a given point in time. It includes agriculture, forestry, pasture, mining, transportation, industrial and commercial activities, residential development, gardens and recreation. Therefore, land use is not just physical but also a result of anthropogenic actions with the natural environment. Land use patterns are dynamic they change according to the needs of society. L. D. Stamp (1948) categorized human needs into six main categories: agriculture, home, food, transportation, communication, defence, and recreation. As populations grow and economies grow, the competition among different land uses has increased. Often, productive agricultural land is diverted to non-agricultural uses, a situation that greatly impacts the sustainable, the country's food security in the longer run. Upon withdrawal from agricultural application, the land rarely

Received: 3 August 2023

Revised: 23 August 2023

Accepted: 30 August 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18126485>

returns to cultivation or only after a long, long time; and with reduced yield. Fast population growth and shifting socio-economic situation require persistent revision of land use processes. Land is a finite resource so it becomes a need for organized planning and appropriate land-use policies, both short-term and long-term objectives. Malegaon city, the administrative headquarters of Malegaon tehsil in Nashik district, Maharashtra, offers a significant case for the study of land use dynamics. Situated along the Mumbai–Agra National Highway located 104 km northeast of Nashik, the tehsil has 143 villages and six towns. The 2011 Census shows Malegaon tehsil covering 1,818.44 sq. km with a population of 955,594 and density of 526 persons per sq. km.

2. Study Area

Malegaon tehsil is in Nashik district of Maharashtra between 20°22' to 20°53' North latitudes and 74°21' to 74°50' East longitudes on an area of 1,818.44 sq. km. The population of tehsil according to 2011 Census was 955,594; 490,303 males, 465,291 females. The literacy rate 70.54 percent is higher among males, reaching 74.25 per cent, and among females, 66.63 per cent. The tehsil is traversed by the Mosam and Girna rivers and supports much agriculture and settlement. Malegaon is flanked by Dhule district to the north, Jalgaon to the northeast, Satana to the east, Chandwad to the south, and Nandgaon to the southwest. The tehsil includes 143 villages and has a monsoon climate with hot summers, moderate winters, and comparatively low rainfall on this leeward side of the Sahyadri ranges.

Prepared by using QGIS

3.Objectives

1. To study the growth of population in Malegaon tehsil over different census periods.
2. To analyse the temporal changes in land use in Malegaon tehsil.
3. To determine the major causes of land use change in the study area.

4.Data base and methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data sources. Secondary data were gathered from Census of India reports to analyse population growth and demographic trends in Malegaon tehsil. Land use statistics were obtained from the District Statistical Abstract of Nashik, Revenue Department records, and published reports of the Government of Maharashtra. Topographical sheets from the Survey of India and satellite imagery were used to understand spatial patterns and changes in land use. To identify causes of land use change, primary data were collected through field surveys, observations, and informal discussions with local farmers and residents. From a methodological point of view, population growth rates were calculated using standard statistical techniques. Land use categories were analysed comparatively over time to identify trends and transformations. Cartographic and GIS techniques were employed to prepare location maps of the study area. The integration of demographic and land use data helped assess the impact of population pressure on land resources and emerging geo-environmental issues in the study area.

5. Discussion-

5.1 Population Growth

Malegaon tehsil, in particular, experienced a consistent and marked increase in population from 1981 till the year 2011. Throughout these thirty years the total population of the tehsil continued to grow reflecting urbanization, economic development, and migration from surrounding rural communities. The population grew from 5,17,000 in 1981 to 9,55,000 in 2011, a cumulative growth of 4,38,000 people. Each decade the population increased but the rate of growth slowly decreased, reflecting changing demographic trends, improved awareness and socio-economic development within the tehsil.

5.2 Population Growth and Decadal Variation

Sr. No.	Year	Total Population	Decadal Variation	Growth in %
01)	1981	517000	-	-
02)	1991	651000	+134000	25.91
03)	2001	790000	+139000	21.35
04)	2011	955000	+165000	20.88
	From 1981 to 2011		438000	

Table no-1 Census and Socio-Economic Abstract- Nashik District

From 1981 till 2011, Malegaon tehsil also had a rapid and continuous population growth with high, steady-state, substantial decadal differences in population over 30 years. In 1981, the entire population of Malegaon tehsil was 5,17,000. That population grew by 1,34,000 by the subsequent decade (1981–1991), rising to 6,51,000 in 1991. The growth was a high 25.91 percent, showing rapid urbanisation, rapid industrial growth and migration from neighbouring rural areas. Its growth rate persisted in 1991–2001. Population grew from 6,51,000 to 7,90,000, an increase of 1,39,000 people. While the actual increase was just above the previous decade’s rates, it fell back to 21.35 percent.

Chart no-1 Population Growth and Decadal Variation

Such decrease indicates a gradual reduction in population growth possibly triggered by literacy, awareness, and family planning activities. In absolute terms, Malegaon tehsil experienced its largest decadal increase between 2001 and 2011. The population increased by 1,65,000 and reached 9,55,000 in 2011. Growth went further down to 20.88 percent — a downward trend of percentage growth. More generally, during the period 1981-2011 the population of Malegaon tehsil grew by 4,38,000 people. While its steady growth reflects that

Malegaon is now a major urban as well as economic center, the declining growth rate also represents demographic passage and better socio-economic conditions.

Chart no-2 Population Growth in Percent

5.3 Population Growth and Decadal Variation of Rural & Urban Population

Sr. No.	Year	Rural	Urban	Rural Decadal Variation	Urban Decadal Variation
1	1981	258000	259000	-	-
2	1991	296000	355000	38000	96000
3	2001	334000	456000	38000	101000
4	2011	368000	587000	34000	131000

Table no-2 Census and Socio-Economic Abstract- Nashik District

Population growth and decadal differences between rural and urban population in Malegaon Tehsil Nashik district reflect strong rural stability and rapid urban growth over the period 1981–2011. In 1981 the rural population was 2,58,000 and urban 2,59,000, rural almost comparable. The rural population increased 38,000 to 2,96,000 between 1981–1991, while the urban population increased approximately 96,000 up to 3,55,000. This means that the urban population has expanded faster with industrial development and migration. Rural population grew 38,000 again between 1991 and 2001, to 3,34,000. Urban population increased 1,01,000 to reach 4,56,000.

Chart no-3 Rural Population and Decadal Variation

The gap widened and it shows the increasing relevance of urban areas in the tehsil. The rural population growth rate was relatively low and ranged from 34,000 to 3,68,000 between 2001 and 2011. But the population of urban areas increased the most in decadal by 1,31,000, reaching 5,87,000 in 2011. Malegaon tehsil exhibits moderate & steady rural growth trend but rapid & growing urban growth. Such a situation reflects the rapid urbanization pattern, availability of jobs and facilities in the cities, resulting in persistent rural-to-urban migration and change of the tehsil’s demographic structure.

Chart no-4 Urban Population and Decadal Variation

6. Temporal variation of land use

The general pattern of land use of Malegaon tehsil exhibits important temporal variability from 1981 to 2011, indicating changes in agricultural practices, urban growth, and land management. The total geographical area of the tehsil was nearly unchanged on the entire period, or approximately 1,93,800 hectares, which showed that changes were mostly related to how land was used, and not to its extent.

Sr. No.	Land Use Particulars (Area in Hectar)	1981	1991	2001	2011
1	Total Geographical area	193800	193800	193800	193765
2	Net sown area	111500	113100	104000	88071
3	Total area of not available for cultivation	25100	5700	30100	26235
4	Cultivable waste	2000	2790	1700	-
5	Total area of Fallow land	14500	6100	11000	7013
6	Area under forest	38600	38600	38600	38580

Table no-3 Socio-Economic Abstract- Nashik District

In 1981, net sown area, 1,11,500 hectares, was the dominant land use category. In 1991, it increased slightly to 1,13,100 hectares; thus agricultural activities and extension of cultivated land. After 1991, however, the net sown area declined dramatically to 1,04,000 hectares in 2001 and 88,071 hectares in 2011. Urbanization, industrial growth, and conversion of farmland to non-agricultural uses have led to more pressure on agriculture. There was great fluctuation in the land that was not suitable for agriculture. It was dramatically reduced from 25,100 hectares in 1981 to 5,700 hectares in 1991, likely resulting from reclamation or reclassification. But this greatly grew to 30,100 hectares in 2001 and also stayed elevated to 26,235 hectares in 2011 due to construction of settlements, roads, industries and other infrastructure. Cultivable waste land decreased gradually, from 2,000 hectares in 1981 to 1,700 hectares in 2001, and had disappeared altogether by 2011. Such land can either be improved or redirected.

Chart no -5 Urban Population and Decadal Variation

The fallow land also varied, from 14,500 hectares in 1981 to 6,100 hectares in 1991, reaching a higher level again in 2001, and then dropping to 7,013 hectares in 2011 indicating changes in rainfall, irrigation, and agriculture practices. That is to say, the amount of forest area stayed close to 38,600 hectares (almost constant) during the period (indicating that the forest area was stable). Thus, Malegaon tehsil's land use patterns indicate a long-term transformation of the land use pattern from agricultural use to non-agricultural use, indicating the implication of population growth and urban development on the land resources.

7. Impact of Population Growth on General Land Use

The correlation between increase in population and overall transformation in land use changes in Malegaon tehsil in Nashik district was clearly noted during the time frame 1981 to 2011. Malegaon tehsil experienced rapid, and continuous population growth over these three decades which put more pressure on available land resources. The total population grew, from 5,17,000 in 1981 to 9,55,000 in 2011, primarily influenced by urbanization, industrial development, and migration from surrounding rural areas. This demographic trend affected the pattern and intensity of land use patterns of the tehsil significantly. One of the main effects of population increase is that net sown area decreases.

While agriculture grew gradually until 1991, land was declining dramatically thereafter, from 1,13,100 ha in 1991 down to 88,071 ha in 2011. This decline is closely related to the increasing demand for residential, industrial, and commercial land to accommodate the burgeoning population, mainly in urban settings. Urban population has seen an exponential increase over the rural population, leading to the transition of much of that agricultural land to the non-agricultural sector. At the same time, after 1991, the area which was not open for cultivation increased greatly, due to extension of settlement, roads, industrial and infrastructure buildings. There were also variation on either cultivable waste and the fallow land, indicating initial efforts to bring the old land to fertile (unused) use following the initial transformation to urban and developmental purposes.

These alterations are a vivid picture of how population pressure changes land use over time. The forest section in Malegaon tehsil, under increasing population pressure, was virtually flat across the study period, indicating a good conservation approach and regulatory control. The correlation between population growth and land use transformation in Malegaon tehsil. Rapid population growth especially in urban areas has caused a decrease in agriculture and a gradual change of dependency from agricultural to non-agricultural land uses. Such a situation emphasizes the necessity of sustainable land use planning for sustainable population growth, agricultural output and environmental safeguards.

Conclusion

Since 1981 to 2011, the land utilization change in Malegaon tehsil have been attributed to rapid population growth, urbanization, and economic development. Ongoing increase in population, particularly in urban areas, and demand related to housing, infrastructure, industries, and transport facilities have resulted in conversion of agricultural land to non-agricultural uses. This trend is evident in the decrease of net sown area and the increase of land not available for cultivation. Agricultural changes, variable rainfall and increased use of waste land additionally contributed to changing land use. In the end, human pressure is the central cause.

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